

PRESERVING CULTURAL IDENTITY THROUGH UNIVERSITY SOCIO-CULTURAL PROGRAMS: INSIGHTS FROM ISABELA STATE UNIVERSITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14219720>

ABSTRACT

Fostering Culture and the Art in educational institutions is a means to help preserve cultural identity and spread appreciation and awareness of the rich heritage and traditions of people. This study aimed to analyze the issues, concerns, and problems encountered in implementing a sociocultural program at Isabela State University in the Philippines. A qualitative single-case design was employed, with purposively chosen student performers and college sociocultural coordinators as the respondents. Data were collected through interviews and analyzed using thematic analysis. The findings revealed several challenges, including lack of stakeholder support, conflicts with academics, and financial constraints. Coordinators addressed these issues through coordination, communication, fundraising, and solicitation activities, while student performers relied on time-management strategies. Despite these challenges, the sociocultural program provided opportunities for increased awareness, skills, and knowledge of culture and the arts, as well as exposure and self-confidence. The study concludes that the program's positive impact on preserving cultural identity can be further enhanced by addressing the identified issues, particularly the lack of stakeholder support. Recommendations include developing a comprehensive cultural development program with specific initiatives for dance, music, and literary and visual arts. The proposed program aims to provide a more defined structure by addressing issues such as budget allocation, partnerships, incentives, and talent development. This study highlights the importance of sociocultural programs in higher education institutions for preserving cultural identity and promoting appreciation of rich heritage and traditions.

Keywords: *Cultural Development, Filipino culture, Performers, Preservation, Socio-cultural program*

INTRODUCTION

Fostering the Culture and the Arts in educational institutions is a means to help preserve cultural identity and spread appreciation and awareness of the rich heritage and traditions of people. So significant is this that Sections 14 to 15 and 17 in Article XIV of the 1987 Constitution even mandates it as follows: “The State shall foster the preservation, enrichment and dynamic evolution of a Filipino national culture. The State shall conserve, promote, and popularize the nations’ historical and cultural heritage and resources as well as artistic creations. The State shall recognize, respect and protect the rights of indigenous cultural communities to preserve and develop their cultural the traditions and institutions.” Similarly, United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Education (UNESCO, 2021) emphasizes how culture enriches education, and vice versa.

In relation to the aforementioned, Crossick and Kaszynska (2016) as cited by Farrell (2016) stipulate that people access the culture and the arts in different settings and through different models. Given this, higher education institutions can be one of the primary means by which people can access culture and arts.

In the Philippines, tertiary education and higher education institutions are vehicles for the inculcation of positive Filipinos and universal human values and instruments for promoting culture and arts. Hence, the Office of Socio-Cultural Affairs was established to provide opportunities for students who are skilled and talented to develop and improve their talents and skills in the fields of dancing, music, visual arts, performing arts, and literary arts, and to give them opportunities to participate in different sociocultural activities. In the process of doing so, they become carriers of national colors in provincial, regional, national, and international events. Activities headed by the Office of Socio-Cultural Affairs also serve as avenues to develop the character of excellence and appreciation of Filipino culture, aesthetic values, knowledge, understanding, and socially desirable traits. The study by Anselmo and Anselmo (2024) on the algopsychalia of out-of-field teachers could provide valuable insights into the challenges faced by educators in preserving cultural identity through university sociocultural programs at Isabela State University. Their qualitative inquiry into the experiences of teachers working outside their areas of expertise may shed light on potential difficulties in implementing culturally relevant programs effectively. By integrating this research, the paper on Isabela State University's efforts to preserve cultural identity could explore how the algopsychalia of faculty members might impact the design, implementation, and success of sociocultural initiatives. This integration could offer a more comprehensive understanding of the complexities involved in maintaining cultural heritage within the university setting, considering both institutional efforts and psychological experiences of the educators responsible for these programs.

The Sociocultural Affairs Office of Isabela State University developed the following quality objectives: to encourage students' development in the preservation, development, and promotion of culture and the arts through dance, music, visual arts, performing arts, and literary arts; and to promote students' welfare and satisfaction through the implementation of efficient and effective student services.

To achieve these objectives, the Socio-Cultural Affairs Office established different organizations, such as the STEPS Dance Troupe, which focuses on showcasing, preserving, and promoting contemporary, indigenous, and folkdances of the Philippines, and the ISU Band and Choir, which cater to the appreciation, learning, and mastery of different musical genres among student musicians. The office also conducts annual culture and arts festivals to develop and improve students' skills in the fields of dance, music, performing arts, visual arts, instrumental arts, and literary arts. The winners and selected performers then underwent a series of training and rehearsals in preparation for university, regional, and national Culture and the Arts Festivals.

The Office also ensures that university student performers are constantly trained to hone their artistry further. Dance training workshops were held in different dance genres to familiarize them with indigenous dance traditions. Due to the vast repertoire of performers, they have been invited to perform in different activities and programs of schools in various events conducted by the Cauayan City LGU, the DOST, NGOs, private organizations and establishments, and other private and government offices in the region. Their exemplary performance has also allowed troupe to be chosen by the National Commission for Culture and the Arts to perform in the International Dance Exchange on Air 2020.

The Socio-Cultural Affairs Office also upholds its aim to promote culture and arts through its extension project entitled "BAYLE KULTURA De Cauayan: A dance training workshop for different schools of Dep.Ed -Cauayan City". The Said Project was in partnership with the City LGU and DepEd. During the National Arts Month Celebration, the Office was recognized by LGU Cauayan for its unparalleled and excellent contribution to the local arts council, which contributed to the success of City Tourism projects and advocacy.

While the ISU Cauayan Campus Socio-Cultural Affairs Office has garnered numerous recognitions of its projects in spreading cultural and artistic awareness and appreciation, there are certain issues and concerns that create difficulties for performers. For this reason, the researcher conducted this study as he aimed to determine and analyze the issues and opportunities and their impact on the implementation of the sociocultural program at the ISU Cauayan Campus. By doing so, the role of the socio-cultural affairs office as a venue for the promotion and development of culture and arts through various dance, musical, and performing arts programs can be further enhanced and strengthened. The results of the different studies under this study will be beneficial in the preparation of an action plan and sociocultural development program.

Research Objectives

The primary objective of this study is to analyze the issues, concerns, and problems encountered in the implementation of the sociocultural program at Isabela State University. Specifically, it aims to

1. determine the problems and issues encountered by sociocultural performers and college-socio-cultural directors in different socio-cultural programs, and
2. collect and identify suggestions and recommendations to solve issues, concerns, and problems in the implementation of the socio-cultural program and as a basis for the improvement of socio-cultural programs

METHODOLOGY

Owing to the nature of the objectives and data available for informing the study, a qualitative single-case design was used. This allowed the researcher to identify the details of the respondents' behaviors and insights about a certain phenomenon.

The respondents comprised five purposively chosen 5 student performers from the Socio-Cultural Affairs Office in dance, musical, literary arts, visual arts, and instrumental programs. Also, the 5 College Socio-Cultural Coordinators of ISU-Cauayan City Campus were included, The study was conducted at the Isabela State University-Cauayan City Campus for the S.Y. 2021-2022. An interview was conducted with the respondents, and the data they provided were duly analyzed using thematic analysis. The transcripts of the interview were organized, synthesized, and examined for common statements and patterns which were then grouped into themes

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Through the interviews, the respondents, consisting of the coordinators and student performers, were able to share their perspectives and insights about the implementation of the sociocultural programs in the university as follows:

Problems and Issues in the Different Socio-Cultural Programs

1. Stakeholders' Support

Both the coordinator and student respondents cited their concerns about the support given to them and the sociocultural affairs in which they were involved. Coordinator 1 (C1) for example stated:

C1: Lack of support from colleagues at our school. They do not support us when there are sociocultural competitions both online and face-to-face, especially during campus culture and the arts festival and other contested activities organized by the sociocultural affairs office.

The other coordinators also identified the aforementioned issue as one of the challenges they constantly face in the conduct of sociocultural events, in which student performers have to be excused from their synchronous classes due to training and attendance at events. Coordinator 3 (C3) also details the problem as follows:

C3: I think the teacher factor because there are some teachers who are not participative and some who excuse the performer or participants in different socio-cultural events during their rehearsal, during video shooting for virtual programs, and during the actual and face-to-face program and after the program.

Research conducted by Scholl (2016) highlighted a similar issue in US schools. Therefore, although the parents of the student performers and artists were supportive of their sociocultural activities, the teachers and administrators were less supportive. This study established the significance of a supportive school climate and culture for performing arts, as this affected the motivation of coordinators, student performers, and artists to continue excelling.

In relation to the aforementioned, Student 3 (S3) and Student 4 shared their experience of this lack of support, as follows:

S3: Some faculty are not considerate specially in the submission of requirements and other tasks because even if I sent an excused letter , they deducted my points/grade in the assessment tasks submi

S4: I am always invited to perform musical, instrumental, and even dance on campus and outside campus...I am not excused in some of my classes despite the fact that I presented excuse letters.

The same situation was experienced by the rest of the student performers who participated in this study, thus proving that this issue was common among student performers at Isabela State University. In the long run, this condition can be detrimental to the success of a socio-cultural program. According to Tait et al. (2019), attitudinal barriers, such as those experienced by respondents from important stakeholders, are far more challenging than the practical barriers faced by sociocultural and arts programmes in schools. Attitudinal barriers have also been found to be a factor that can discourage students from engaging with the arts. It should be noted that the immediate school community was the primary support for art programs. This includes the involvement of administrators, coordinators, and teachers who embrace and foster a climate of consensus to support sociocultural undertakings (National Association of Music Merchants Foundation 2021).

On the other hand, school administrations and many educators do not give it the priority it deserves because high-stakes testing does not test it; it is not perceived

as equally important to other academic courses, such as science and mathematics (Crescencio, 2019).

2. Conflict with Academics

In relation to the aforementioned, many student performers also expressed their concern about how their participation in the sociocultural program's activities and events negatively impacted their academics, as they were not given consideration when they missed classes. Student 5 (S5) said:

S5: Time for rehearsal and proper programming, which is in conflict with some of our classes... Some faculty members are inconsiderate: they did not excuse us even if it was a campus event.

Dunstan (2016) mentions how restrictive the climate of accountability is for art programs in schools; thus, current educational practices are perceived as a threat to the survival and development of art programs in educational institutions. There is perennial pressure for schools to improve academic performance; hence, the disinterest of teachers in supporting and considering the situation of student performers is rationalized. One coordinator shared:

C3: Some students were afraid of missing lessons. Therefore, instead of joining, they preferred to attend classes.

If student performers obtain the opportunities to be excused from their classes to attend socio-cultural events and activities, they still encounter problems such as those cited by Students 2 (S2) and 4 (S4):

S2: Rehearsal and during the program. This is in conflict with the findings of some studies.

S4: I am always invited to perform musical, instrumental, and even dance on campus and outside campus, which affects my time to make my assignments and review my lessons for the quizzes.

The adverse effects of missing classes ultimately impact not only the academic standing of students, but also their opportunities for financial support. This was the case for Student 5 (S5).

S5: I am not qualified to avail the sociocultural scholarship due to incomplete grades caused by my late submission of requirements.

Scholars are required to maintain a certain GPA at Isabela State University. If students cannot maintain their grades, there is always the danger that they will lose scholarship opportunities.

According to Pollock (2020), class attendance and conflict with extra-curricular commitments are common problems for students at all levels. In the case of the socio-cultural program, it can be said that its extra-curricular load is really heavy given the nature of its activities and events. Given this, it is no surprise that the academics of student performers suffer if they cannot manage their time properly.

3. *Financial Constraints*

Financial constraints were also cited as a problem for both the coordinator and student respondents. According to Coordinator 3 (C3),

C3: Financial matter because there is no allotted budget used by participants, especially during Intrams or Campus Culture, the Arts Festival, and other events conducted in the school.

Coordinator 5 (C5) also stated:

C5: ...lack of financial support during preparations, lack of materials to be used in our performances, and support from other faculty members.

Student performers cited a similar concern:

C1: As a performer of the ISU Socio-Cultural Group, I encountered several problems upon the dancers and the materials needed such as cosmetics, props , etc... same of our costumes did not function (zipper, buttons, etc,)

Other respondents also mentioned a lack of support for food and snacks during rehearsals, training, and the events themselves. Notably, funding is a universal concern for many art programmes in school systems worldwide. For example, in the United States, Crescencio (2019) explains that while arts are recognized for their transformative capacity among students, they are also frequently under threat in terms of budget cuts and standardized testing. In the United Kingdom, Phillips (2019) also reported that many consider arts as 'not economically worthwhile; hence, funding for such programs in schools is reduced. Similar to the lack of support, a lack of funding has also been seen as detrimental for student performers to continue engaging in sociocultural activities, as these require expenses for costumes, set designs, equipment, and even stipends. In the long run, the quality of students' performance and their motivation to continue performing are compromised. Coordinator 4 (C4) stated the following:

C4: Lack of budget for performance that makes materials far from the authentic literature.

Mechanisms Used to Overcome Problems and Issues Encountered

Despite the aforementioned issues and challenges, it is fortunate that the coordinator and student respondents of the sociocultural program worked to remedy and resolve them. Upon questioning the mechanisms employed, the respondents identified the following:

1. Coordination and Communication

From the perspective of the coordinators, many of them identified constant communication with stakeholders as a mechanism they employed to overcome some of their problems in the socio-cultural program. Coordinator 1 (C1), for example, states his reasons for constant coordination and communication:

C1: I coordinated with our heads to encourage faculty and students to participate in different sociocultural activities.

For Coordinator 1, coordination and communication are instrumental in ensuring the presence and participation of other faculty members and students in the events and activities of the Sociocultural Affairs Office. Coordinator 2 (C2) does the same thing but his purpose is to provide information on the benefits of participating and joining the events and activities:

C2: I tell them about the advantages of joining and the possibility of them competing with nationals and being able to travel.

Coordinator 2's mindset was reflected on the study of Pan and Gan (2019) in which it was found out that monetary and honorary reward as well as teachers' support were significant in motivating students to participate and join in extra-curricular activities. These are also related to Bayat's (2015) statement that student engagement in extra-curricular activities is evidenced by cognitive, emotional, and behavioral aspects.

Coordinator 3 (C3), on the other hand, communicates with other faculty members, the student performers' teachers specifically, to ensure that they receive the necessary support:

C3: I personally talked to their instructors/professors to excuse them from their classes and, if possible, give them incentives by giving them additional points in their quizzes, exams, or even in their final grades.

The significance of coordination and communication in the implementation of sociocultural programs was discussed by Biag et al. (2015) in their study. They discussed how systematized coordination shaped the success of the programme.

2. Fundraising and Solicitation Activities

For coordinators 4 (C4) and 5 (C5), the mechanism they practiced to address the limits of financial support involved engaging in fundraising and solicitation activities. They said:

C4: We conducted fund raising activities through the effort of the SBO Officers through collection of plastic and bottles by our students

C5: We also tried to solicit financial support from other organizations and be creative in costumes and props.

According to Hokins and Friedman (2019), the practice of soliciting funds for sociocultural programs is acceptable as long as the organization in question clearly defines what solicitation is for and why it is being done.

3. *Time Management*

For the student performers, the problem they were most concerned with was the conflict between their academic obligations and their participation in sociocultural program activities and events. They cited the following as the mechanisms employed to remedy the conflict:

S2: I set a limit on what I am doing, and I always ensure that I will start the task early. I always managed my time in my academic activities and participated in various visual art-contested activities.

Student 2 (S2) indicated the importance of time management in helping her balance her studies and engaging in the sociocultural program. Other student performers shared the same perspective. Students 3 (S3) and 4 (S4), for example, the state

S3: Time management for attending practice. Time management between study and rehearsal, and I also requested that the Director for Socio-cultural Affairs conduct rehearsal every Friday, especially all of us, are available that time.

S4: I see that I submit all my requirements and have a special quiz through the Director of Sociocultural Affairs. I realized that proper time management is important for performers. I should prioritize my study.

In relation to the above-mentioned statements, Roll (2015) stipulated that students engaged in extra-curricular activities acknowledged the positive impact of time management in helping them continue their dual roles in school.

Perceived Opportunities in the Socio-Cultural Affairs Program Implementation

Various studies have identified the benefits and opportunities of engaging in sociocultural programs. However, from the perspective of the respondents, this is what they have identified.

1. *Increased Awareness, Skills and Knowledge in Culture and Arts*

The coordinators cited opportunities to hone their expertise as educators and coaches as their foremost benefit afforded to them. Coordinator 1 (C1) specifically identified how his work with the socio-cultural program gave him the chance to increase his knowledge:

C1: I attended a series of training sessions and seminars related to sociocultural events.

The same can be said for Coordinator 2:

C2: The sociocultural affairs office allowed me to go to different events to further observe and benchmark the best practices that I could implement to improve our team as well as my talents. The social office also allowed me to speak and negotiate if there were cases that needed to be resolved, which would result in a better working environment for delegates. I also appreciate the social office because they do all the possible means to generate funds for their programs, which will turn into prizes that would benefit its participants.

For student performers, their engagement with the socio-cultural affairs at the university also enabled them to enhance their knowledge of culture and arts. Student 1 (S1) stated,

S1: It allows me to learn the different genres of dance such as hips with their genres and ethnic dances. Moreover, it helps me boost my confidence, interact with others, and overcome my fears of facing many people. Thus, this organization develops self-esteem, changes behavior, and matures self.

It should be noted that Student 1 also added that his confidence and social skills improved, as shown in the aforementioned statement. Student 4 (S4) stated,

S4: It improves my instrumental, musical, and dance talents.

In alignment with the experiences of coordinators, Biag et al. (2015) also reported such advantages in an arts program implemented in the US. Participants, including teachers, described how the program benefited them in terms of creating spaces that fostered physical, temporal, intellectual, and artistic creativity.

2. *Exposure and Self-Confidence*

Engaging and participating in the sociocultural program also exposed the respondents, which helped them widen their perspectives and their social and professional contacts with other pertinent entities. Coordinator 2 (C2), for example, stipulated:

C2: Opportunity to participate in university and regional sociocultural competition. I also attended a series of training sessions and seminars related to sociocultural events.

Similarly, the other coordinators cited identical experiences.

C3: Visited different places as assigned coaches in some events and participated in different training and seminars sponsored by the sociocultural affairs office.

C4: Opportunity to participate in university and regional sociocultural competition. I also attended a series of training sessions and seminars related to sociocultural events.

In line with this, student performers shared their experiences as follows:

S3: It also develops and improves my talent in dancing and singing and performs in different events organized in the campus and in other agencies.

S5: I showcase my musical and instrumental talents in different events at the schools and other organizations that invited us to perform. When I invited me to perform outside school-like events of the LGU Cauayan and other private organizations, I allotted an honorarium for me. I also participated in a university sociocultural competition in music and bands.

These statements indicate how sociocultural programs can become avenues for formative educational opportunities (Bowen and Kisida 2021). This was also stated in the work of Ewing (2018), who mentioned how engagement in the arts increases students' communicative and collaborative literacy, in addition to the usual artistic and creative benefits. The respondents of the current study, consisting of both coordinators and student performers, all displayed said benefits, as all of them indicated how the university's sociocultural program afforded them to engage with other people who are involved in similar undertakings, travel to different places, and perform in various events that enriched their experience in the arts.

Conclusions

The implementation of the sociocultural program at Isabela State University faces several challenges, including lack of stakeholder support, conflicts with academics, and financial constraints. Despite these issues, the program provides valuable opportunities for increased awareness, skills, and knowledge of culture and arts, as well as exposure and self-confidence for both coordinators and student performers. Coordinators address challenges through coordination, communication, fundraising, and solicitation activities, while student performers rely on time-management strategies. The program's positive impact on preserving cultural identity and promoting appreciation of rich heritage and traditions is evident, but its effectiveness can be further enhanced by addressing identified issues, particularly the lack of stakeholder support. To improve the program, it is recommended that a comprehensive cultural development program be formulated and implemented with specific initiatives for dance, music, literary, and visual art. The proposed program should provide a more defined structure for the university's existing sociocultural program to address issues such as budget allocation, partnerships, incentives, and talent development. This study underscores the importance of

sociocultural programs in higher education institutions for preserving cultural identity and fostering appreciation of cultural heritage, while also highlighting the need for continued support and improvement to maximize their potential benefits.

Recommendations

1. Develop a comprehensive cultural development program that encompasses specific initiatives for dance, music, literary, and visual art. This structured approach provides a clear framework for existing sociocultural programs.
2. Addressing the lack of stakeholder support by implementing strategies to increase engagement and participation from various university departments and external partners.
3. Improving budget allocation for the program to alleviate financial constraints and ensure sustainable funding for cultural activities and events.
4. Partnerships should be established with local cultural organizations, government agencies, and other educational institutions to expand resources and opportunities for cultural exchange.
5. Introduce incentives for both coordinators and student performers to encourage continued participation and dedication to the program.
6. Implement talent development initiatives to nurture and cultivate artistic skills among students, potentially creating a pipeline for future performers and cultural ambassadors.
7. Enhance communication channels between program coordinators, university administrations, and academic departments to minimize conflicts with academic schedules and increase overall support for the program.
8. Develop a formal time management training program for student performers to help them balance their academic responsibilities with cultural activities.
9. Create a system for regular program evaluation and feedback collection from participants, stakeholders, and audience members to continuously improve and adapt the programme.
10. Explore innovative fundraising strategies and solicitation activities to diversify funding sources and reduce reliance on limited university budgets.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical considerations by respecting the cultural heritage and identity of the indigenous and local communities involved. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring voluntary involvement and clear understanding of the study's purpose and scope. The research maintained confidentiality by anonymizing personal information and protecting participants' privacy. Additionally, the study is sensitive to cultural expressions and traditions, thus avoiding the exploitation or

misrepresentation of cultural elements. The findings will be shared with the community, promoting mutual respect, and reinforcing cultural pride and preservation.

Acknowledgments

The authors express their sincere gratitude to the Sociocultural Office of Isabela State University for providing the funding and support required to conduct this study. Special thanks are extended to Prof. Charlie T. Anselmo for his invaluable guidance and expertise in editing this manuscript for publication. His insights and constructive insights.

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